

How Do Users Forage on OGD Portals? An Information Foraging Perspective through Trace Data Analysis

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Supplementary Material

This is the supplementary material describing the data preprocessing and analysis.

0.1. Data

The raw data is extracted from user interaction on the portal. Each user action is a dictionary of key value pairs. A clear structure is provided below.

```
{'timestamp': 'example',  
'user_ip_addr': 'example',  
'hostname': 'example',  
'user_id': 'example',  
'sso_identifieur': 'example',  
'dataset_id': ['example1', 'example2'],  
'domain_id': 'example',  
'api_type': 'example',  
'api': 'example',  
'query_string': 'example',  
'custom_attributes': 'example',  
'format': 'example',  
'size_res': 'example',  
'nhits': 'example',  
'exec_time': 'example',  
'request_aborted': 'example',  
'facet': 'example',  
'in_error': 'example',  
'error': 'example',  
'attachment_id': 'example',  
'image_id': 'example',  
'filename': 'example',  
'user_agent': 'example',  
'referrer': 'example',  
'embed_type': 'example',  
'embed_referrer': 'example',  
'domain_uuid': 'example',  
'parent_domain': 'example',  
'zone': 'example',  
'query_field': 'example',  
'query_text': 'example',  
'bot': 'example',  
'mobile': 'example',  
'action': 'example',  
'federated': 'example',  
'attributes': 'example'}
```

Different steps were needed to clean the data and perform session clustering. We provide a description of these steps. In the remainder we refer to each key as a variable to smooth the explanation.

0.2. Session construction

User interaction logs from the Namur open data portal were transformed into sessions using a standard inactivity-based heuristic. Events were first grouped by a user identifier constructed from the IP address, user agent, and host name. Within each user timeline, a new session was initiated whenever the time elapsed between two consecutive events exceeded 30 minutes. Sessions were therefore defined as sequences of temporally contiguous actions performed by the same user without prolonged inactivity.

Some practical considerations :

- Bot-related activity was filtered out. Actions flagged as bot traffic were removed using the boolean variable `bot`. In addition, residual automated traffic was identified through the `user_agent` field, notably entries such as “GPTBot1.3” or “https:openai.comgptbot”, and these records were also excluded.
- A composite user identifier “`user_key`” was defined by combining the variables : “`user_ip_addr`”, “`user_agent`” and “`hostname`”. The dataset was then sorted by “`user_key`” and “`timestamp`” to ensure the correct temporal ordering of events within each user timeline.

- For each “user_key” the time gap between each action and the preceding one was computed. These time differences were used to assign a “session_index” enabling actions to be grouped into sessions: when the elapsed time between two consecutive actions exceeded 30 minutes, the latter action was marked as the beginning of a new session.

0.3. Action-level variable construction

Each logged event was interpreted as an action and enriched with variables describing where the user was interacting with the portal and what they were doing. The user interface context (page_type) captured the portal module in which the action occurred (dataset exploration, editorial or dashboard pages, analytical views), while action classes (action_class) summarized the functional intent of requests (search and discovery, dataset inspection, value extraction). Administrative interactions associated with publisher back-office interfaces were identified via the UI context and excluded entirely, as they represent data management activity rather than public data use. Query-related behavior was characterized by identifying the presence of query constraints (q= parameters) and distinguishing between UI-generated constraints and likely user-typed input, as well as between structured and free-text syntax. Facet-based and query-based refiltering events were detected by changes in constraint signatures between consecutive actions within a session.

Some practical considerations :

- Session length was computed as the time difference between the timestamps of the first and last actions within each session.
- String variables such as “action”, “api”, “api_type”, “custom_attributes”, “query_string” and “referrer” were cleaned and standardized to ensure consistent formatting across the dataset.
- We added “is_dataset_related”: a binary variable to flag actions that are datasets related.
- An additional variable, “page_type”, was created to capture the functional area of the portal in which each action occurred. This variable was derived from “custom_attributes”, and we were able to define five values. The value “explore” means the user is positioned in the part of the

portal where datasets are found, not used. The value “analyze” means the user is in the portal’s analytical workspace. The value “map_geo” means the user is navigating the portal via spatial views. The value “editorial_or_dashboard” means the user is located in a thematic prebuilt views of the portal. The value “publish” means the user is positioned in the data production area of the portal

- We filtered out sessions where the “page_type” value is “publish”, because these relate to users with administrative access rather than lay users consulting the portal.
- Similarly to “page_type”, we defined a variable, “action_class”, based on “action”. “action_class” encapsulates what the user is really doing.
- A user can refilter either by using a text query or a facet (filter) available on the portal. Two variables d (“is_refilter_q” and “is_refilter_facet”) capture these subtleties, while another (“is_refilter_any”) simply indicates whether any refiltering was performed by the user for the specific action considered. It is important to highlight that we did not rely solely on a comparison of two consecutive queries to define refiltering. Simple string comparison would falsely detect chart tweaks, UI refreshes, or pagination as “refiltering”. Instead, we tracked specific changes in the refinement parameter “refine” within each query to detect facet-related refiltering. For text query refiltering, we analyzed the structure of the “q=” part of the queries to determine whether it corresponds to a user-entered text query or to a facet generated directly by the interface.
- We added an access channel variable based on the “utm_source” in the query and on the referrer.

0.4. Session-level variable construction

Action-level variables were aggregated at the session level to obtain a compact behavioral representation of each session. Aggregated variables captured (i) session scope (number of unique datasets accessed), (ii) interaction intensity (number of actions), (iii) constraint usage (refiltering rates, query usage rate), and (iv) behavioral composition. Session composition was expressed us-

ing proportions (shares) of actions across UI contexts and action classes, thereby normalizing for session length and enabling meaningful comparison between short and long sessions.

To mitigate the influence of highly skewed distributions typical of web logs, raw count variables were not used directly for clustering. Instead, normalized rates and log-transformed versions of heavy-tailed variables (number of datasets accessed, active session duration) were employed. Sessions consisting of a single action were excluded from clustering, as they represent minimal engagement.

Some practical considerations :

- We aggregated and computed some session levels variables like : “session_duration_sec”, “n_actions” (number of actions) among others.
- We also computed ratio like “refilter_any_rate”, “dataset_event_rate” which respectively reflect the shares of actions that are flagged as refilter and the share of actions that are dataset related. For each of the variables “page_type” and “action_class”, we computed at session level the share of their different values in each session generating a specific variable per value.

0.5. Variable selection for clustering

The final set of variables used for clustering was deliberately restricted to a small number of normalized, behaviorally independent variables. Variables were selected to represent complementary dimensions of user behavior: exploration versus exploitation, use of constraints, scope of data access, and distribution of interaction across portal interfaces. Redundant variables (raw counts alongside normalized rates), low-variance features,

and infrastructure-driven actions were excluded to avoid overweighting technical artifacts or duplicating information already captured at a higher level of abstraction. Importantly, clustering was performed on transformed variables, while interpretation relied exclusively on raw, meaningful session variables. The full list of variables used for clustering is presented in the paper.

0.6. Clustering procedure

Prior to clustering, selected variables were standardized using z-score to zero mean and unit variance to avoid scale or unit related distortion. The clustering was performed on the scaled features using HDBSCAN, a density-based algorithm. This clustering algorithm was chosen for several reasons : (i) it is suitable for data with heterogeneous densities as we can expect for the sessions level data we extracted; (ii) it does not require an initial number of cluster; (iii) it labels ambiguous data points as noise so rather than forcing them into a cluster and (iv) by construction allow robust cluster identification based on their stability across multiple neighborhood scales. Using a minimal cluster size of 150 and a minimal sample of 20 (number of data point need to estimate local density) we identified a total of 5 session clusters and a group of sessions labeled as noise.

0.7. Robustness check

The main cluster structures persisted across variations in minimal sample (10, 15, 20) and minimal cluster size (110, 120, 130, 140, 150, 160, 170, 180, 190, 200), with only minor changes affecting low-density boundary points and noise assignments. This consistency indicates that the identified clusters reflect stable structures rather than artefacts of a specific parameter configuration.